

Cram on Psychological Climate and Organisational Climate of Women Entrepreneurs

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ABSTRACT

Achieving gender equality through various special empowerment measures within the legal framework of the state is one of the objectivities of welfare states in the modern period. Education is the first step towards empowerment and the most crucial factor in the overall development of an individual as well as a nation. The situation of women in our world today is very important. There are many differences between richer and poorer countries. Psychological climate is defined as individual employee perceptions of their work environment. The organizational climate is a concept "perceived" by employees as well as provided by the organization. Some experts think of entrepreneurs as people who are willing to take risks that other people are not. The investigator had an aim to study about the Psychological and Organisational Climate of Working Women. Normative Survey method was adopted to collect data in Puducherry UT. After the analysis, the result explored as there is a deep relationship between Organisational Climate and Psychological Climate of Women.

"I measure the progress of a community by the degree of progress which women have achieved"

-Dr. B. R. Ambedkar

Women are the real Architects of Society

-Harriet Beecher Stowe

A Woman is the full circle. Within her is the power to Create, Nurture and transform.

-Diane Mariechild

1. Introduction

The situation of women in our world today is very important. There are many differences between richer and poorer countries. They do not want to stay at home any longer. The situation of women is different. Many of them are at home, do the household chores and care for their children. Helping women in the Third World is very important and can slow down the population explosion. One of the key factors is Education. Women who go to school and maybe later on study at a university have higher chances of getting a job. Women are in top positions as a result of their perseverance tasks. They compete with the other gender in all walks of the life.

Achieving gender equality through various special empowerment measures within the legal framework of the state is one of the objectivities of welfare states in the modern period. Education is the first step towards empowerment and the most crucial factor in the overall development of an individual as well as a nation. It liberates the mind, opening up new horizon, new hope, opportunities and self-confidence and further equips the people with knowledge, skill, self respect and freedom to participate, sustain and excel in their life.

Women are the Opportunities Experts, The Networking Professionals, The Relationship Specialist and The Natural Givers.

2. Psychological Climate

Psychological Climate is nothing but that how we are looking our climate and how we can able to change it accordingly to us. Today many people are lacking in this change. So what they are looking for the job they want and they are restricting themselves that they can do only this instead of doing others. If a person have strong Psychological strength surely he/ she can change the climate according to him/ her.

It is a combination of mental health, behaviorism and the climate around us. This combination makes us to adopt the situation easily and we can succeed anything easily in any situation.

Psychological climate is defined as individual employee perceptions of their work environment.

3. Organizational Climate

The organizational climate is a concept "perceived" by employees. Importantly, it is dependent on a value judgment which can vary greatly from person to person. The organizational climate affects productivity, motivation and employee behavior. Organizational climate, on the other hand, is often defined as the recurring patterns of behavior, attitudes and feelings that characterize life in the organization, while an organization culture tends to be deep and stable.

4. Entrepreneurship

Some experts think of entrepreneurs as people who are willing to take risks that other people are not. Others define them as people who start and build successful businesses. Thinking about the first of these definitions, entrepreneurship doesn't necessarily involve starting your own business. Many people who don't work for themselves are recognized as entrepreneurs within their organizations. Regardless of how

you define an "entrepreneur," one thing is certain: becoming a successful entrepreneur isn't easy. Entrepreneurship is 'an individual's ability to turn ideas into action. It includes creativity, innovation and risk-taking, as well as the ability to plan and manage projects in order to achieve objectives'. Though many researchers have studied the subject, there are no definitive answers. What we do know is that successful entrepreneurs seem to have certain traits in common.

- Personal characteristics.
- Interpersonal skills.
- Critical and creative thinking skills.
- Practical skills.

5. Objective

To assess the impact and relationship between the variables Organisational Climate and Psychological Climate of Women Entrepreneurs.

6. Hypothesis

8. Exploration

S.No	Variables	N	Mean	SD	Organisational Climate	Psychological Climate
1.	Organisational Climate	216	83.14	12.208	1	0.804**
2.	Psychological Climate.		63.94	8.827	0.804**	1

The calculated Pearson Correlation Co-efficient (r-value) value is 0.804 which denotes the highly positive correlation between Organisational Climate and Psychological Climate.

There is no significant relationship among the Women Entrepreneurs towards Organisational Climate and Psychological Climate.

7. Methodology

The research was undertaken to study the Psychological Climate and Organisational Environment, of Working Women for their Empowerment who are residing in the Puducherry. The present study was conducted, following the Survey Method. It was also non-experimental and Descriptive type of research. Survey studies are usually conducted to get information of what exists by studying and analyzing important aspects of the present situation. This was found to be the suitable method of study by the investigator. In the present research the investigator has chosen probability sampling. In the Probability sampling the researcher made use of Stratified Random Sampling process. The investigator has chosen Disproportionate Stratified Random Sampling technique to select the target group. 216 working Women were selected at random comprising the following target groups who were working in Educational Institutions, LIC, Nationalized Bank, Private Employees and Self- Employed.

The Correlational value 0.804 expresses that the Level of Organisational Climate behaviour highly related to the Psychological Climate of the Women Entrepreneurs.

9. Conclusion

To put in a nut shell, Psychological Climate and Organizational Climate are Inter-related. There is a deep relationship between Organisational Climate and Psychological Climate of Women. The level of Organisational Climate highly

related to Psychological Climate of working Women. Finally Psychological Climate depends on the Organisational Climate provided by Organisation.

Reference

1. Zeitlin, Wendy; Claiborne, Nancy; Lawrence, Catherine K.; Auerbach, Charles, Validating the Psychological Climate Scale in Voluntary Child Welfare, *Journal of Research on Social Work Practice*, Sage Publications v26 n2 p203-211 Mar 2016, ISSN-1049-7315
2. Yeadon-Lee, Annie, (2015), Psychological Climates in Action Learning Sets: A Manager's Perspective, *Journal of Research and Practice*, v12 n3 p261-275 2015, Routledge Publications, ISSN-1476-7333
3. Scholtz, Desiree (2018) Service Learning: An Empowerment Agenda for Students and Community Entrepreneurs, *International Journal of Work-Integrated Learning*, v19 n1 p69-79, New Zealand Association for Cooperative Education. University of Waikato, EISSN-2538-1032
4. Zupan, Blaž; Cankar, Franc; SetnikarCankar, Stanka, (2018), The Development of an Entrepreneurial Mindset in Primary Education, *European Journal of Education*, v53 n3 p427-439, Wiley-Blackwell Publications, ISSN-0141-8211
5. Gordon, Jason; Bursuc, Vlad (2018), Law and Entrepreneurship Education: A Proposed Model for Curriculum Development, *Journal of Legal Studies Education*, v35 n1 p123-141, Wiley-Blackwell, ISSN-0896-5811
6. https://www.mindtools.com/pages/article/newCDV_76.htm
7. https://skillspanorama.cedefop.europa.eu/sites/default/files/EUSP_AH_Entrepreneurial_0.pdf